

WATER RESERVOIRS AND THE WAR IN UKRAINE: ENVIRONMENTAL PROBLEMS

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Abstract

The aim of this article is to analyze the consequences of the military invasion of the Russian Federation on February 24, 2022 on the water bodies of Ukraine. In particular, this article presents an analysis of the consequences of military operations on reservoirs.

In order to prevent the enemy from reaching the dam of the Kyiv Reservoir and to protect Kyiv from the aggressor in late February-early March of this year, the sluice of the pumping station on the Kozarovychi Dam was blown up. Because, the possible destruction of this dam could have enormous destructive consequences for the entire cascade of reservoirs and the territories adjacent to them. As a result, a huge area of about 2,500 hectares of the Irpin' floodplain was flooded, fundamentally changing both the military and the environmental situation.

Also, Russian troops launched a missile attack on the dam of the Karachuniv Reservoir near the Kryvyi Rih city. The water level in the Ingulets River rose sharply by 2 meters, flooding the territories near the river, including part of the Kryvyi Rih city. The ecological condition of this territory was significantly damaged, private buildings were heavily flooded. Water quality in this river has deteriorated, the content of nitrogen and other elements has increased in it. The Oskol Reservoir in the east of Ukraine was also destroyed. As a result of the leakage of a significant amount of water, the muddy bottom has been exposed to water and is subject to wind erosion. The hydrological regime of the coastal area has changed. Rare species of flora and young fish population have been lost.

Destruction of reservoirs and damage to the environment will continue until the war ends. And it is necessary to do everything possible so that it ends as soon as possible.

Keywords: war, water reservoir, dams, military invasion, destruction, environmental problems, flooding.

DOI: 10.21303/2504-5695.2022.002664

1. Introduction

The military invasion of the Russian Federation into Ukraine, which began on February 24, 2022 and continues to this day, caused not only numerous victims of the military and civilian residents of Ukraine and the destruction of housing and infrastructure in cities and villages, but also caused significant water and environmental problems. The problem of large and small reservoirs, which is professionally close to the authors of this work, is among them. After all, the use of these water reservoirs for both aggressive and defensive military operations creates extreme threats to the life and health of people and the ecological state of the environment [1–4].

2. Materials and methods

In the pre-war years, Ukrainian environmentalists conducted a detailed comprehensive study of both the cascade of large reservoirs on the Dnipro (Dnieper) River and numerous reservoirs on many rivers of Ukraine and beyond, including the authors of this publication [5–8]. Field terrestrial and water routes, long-term stationary observations, in-depth analytical studies,

cartographic and aerospace materials were used. But the situation changed dramatically with the beginning of the war. For the study of environmental problems in the temporarily occupied territory, our scientists mainly have access to materials from remote sensing of the Earth, in particular images from Sentinel, Landsat and other satellites [9, 10]. And in the territories freed from the occupiers, the facts of chemical pollution and technogenic disturbance of water bodies and soils, which pose a threat to people's lives and economic activities, are first of all studied [11]. An important source is the materials of the mass media, which quickly spread the facts of significant environmental violations as a result of military operations. From a large mass of information, we are currently considering the problem of the destructive impact of the war on reservoirs, which are a vital source of drinking, municipal, industrial and agricultural water supply [12–15].

3. Results and discussion

The most dangerous situation in the first days of the war was at the top of the Dni-pro (Dnieper) cascade of reservoirs. The occupying troops rapidly advanced along the right bank of the Kyiv Reservoir towards Kyiv, trying to seize the Vyshgorod Dam of this reservoir. And the possible destruction of this dam could have huge destructive consequences for the entire cascade of reservoirs and the territories adjacent to them. In particular, such a huge flow of water could not safely pass through the Kaniv reservoir, the second in the cascade. The consequence of this would be the flooding of the southern part of our capital Kyiv and a large area up to the city of Ukrainka with large civilian casualties. And the consequences of the destruction of the following reservoirs of the Dni-pro (Dnieper) Cascade are difficult to imagine.

The problem of the impossibility of passing extreme water flows through the Kaniv Reservoir and possible catastrophic flooding and inundation of the southern part of Kyiv due to this has been analyzed by Ukrainian scientists for a long time [6, 7, 16, 17]. It arose due to the intensive development of the Kaniv Reservoir coast, which was not foreseen by the project, which was supposed to be a temporary accumulator of extreme floodwaters, as well as the creation of new lands in the water area of the reservoir with dredges (Fig. 1, 2).

Fig. 1. Dni-pro (Dnieper) cascade of reservoirs and reasons impossibility of passing extreme water flows through the Kaniv Reservoir: *a* – water reservoirs: 1 – Kyiv, 2 – Kaniv, 3 – Kremenchuk, 4 – Kamianske, 5 – Dni-pro, 6 – Kakhovka; *b* – new land creation by dredges in the upper part of the Kaniv reservoir

Taking into account the great danger of possible flooding for the population of the capital and the surrounding territories, Ukrainian scientists quickly developed a cartographic forecast in two versions, depending on the scale of the Kyiv Reservoir Dike destruction (Fig. 3). It should be noted, that dam break analysis and the risks associated with it is very actual problem at the global level [18–22].

Fig. 2. Intensive development of new lands created by dredges in the water area of the Kaniv Reservoir: *a* – view of new lands on satellite image; *b* – buildings on newly developed lands by dredges (photo by Volodymyr Starodubtsev)

Fig. 3. Forecast of the possible area of inundation because of the destruction of the Kyiv Reservoir dam: *a* – under possible dam breach 200 m long; *b* – under possible dam breach 100 m long [17]

But tragic events unfolded unpredictably for the aggressor in late February-early March of this year on the right bank of the Kyiv Reservoir, where the Irpin River flows (or rather, is pumped by a pumping station) into this reservoir. Huge convoys of the aggressor's military equipment headed in those days in the direction of the Kyiv city to seize our capital. But it was on the approaches to the Irpin' River that they were stopped by our heroic defenders. In order not to allow the enemy to go to Kyiv, a bridge over the Irpin River near the village of Demydiv was destroyed, which could not be bypassed due to the swampy floodplain. Therefore, the aggressor tried to break through the Kozarovychi Dam, which protected the reclamation floodplain of the Irpin' River from being flooded by the waters of the Kyiv Reservoir (Fig. 4, 5). However, in that critical situation for our capital, it was decided to blow up the sluice of the pumping station on this dam in order not to allow the enemy to the dam of the Kyiv Reservoir and to the capital of Ukraine. A huge area of about 2,500 hectares of the Irpin' floodplain was flooded, fundamentally changing both the military and

the environmental situation. The enemy did not reach Kyiv, and the water of the Kyiv Reservoir in this cold season flooded not only the reclaimed meadows and pastures of the floodplain of the Irpin' River, but also flooded the buildings and the residents' homesteads of the Demydiv village outskirts (Fig. 5, 6).

Fig. 4. Reclaimed floodplain of the Irpin' River that is protected from the water of the Kyiv Reservoir by the Kozarovychi Dam, and the Demydiv village (Sentinel-2, 2021-05-10): 1 – dam, 2 – hydro-ameliorative system, 3 – Demydiv village, 4 – bridge over the Irpin' river

Fig. 5. Destruction of the lock of the Kozarovychi Dam (1) and the bridge over the Irpin' River (2) to stop the aggressor's troops (Sentinel-2, 2022-03-11)

However, the local community bravely endured this temporary calamity. Therefore, by carrying out such unpredictable actions for the enemy, it was possible to avoid the pain of dangerous and large-scale threats that could have arisen as a result of undermining by Russian troops the much more dam of the Kyiv Reservoir.

What kind of territory is this, which has undergone powerful environmental changes, but which are necessary for the defense of the country? As part of the Kyiv HPP and Reservoir project, it is officially called "Protection of the Irpin' River Floodplain". This protection was carried out by the 1.4 km long Kozarovychi dam and a pumping station built in its body, which pumped Irpin' water (over 60 m³/s) into the Kyiv reservoir. The protected territory with an area of about 2.5 thousand hectares was used mainly as meadows and hayfields. The soil cover here is diverse, hydromorphic and semi-hydromorphic soils (from meadow-swamp to swamp and peat-swamp) predominate (according to our field research).

Fig. 6. State of the Irpin' River floodplain after the reconstruction of the Kozarovychi dam lock and the bridge over the Irpin River, but before water pumping from floodplain (Sentinel-2, 2022-06-19):
1 – dam, 2 – flooded territory, 3 – Demydiv village, 4 – restored crossing over the Irpin River

Land reclamation of this massif in peacetime was carried out by a network of drainage canals, which are partially silted up and need cleaning. Hydrotechnical structures also need repair. Groundwater in the summer lies mainly at a depth of 0.5–1.5 m, depending on the state of the drainage system, the topography of the area and the water content of the year. It is important to note that even before the war, reconstruction of the defense of this massif was planned. Therefore, it will be possible to return to this project already after the victory in the war. In addition, a sharp discussion among ecologists and farmers regarding the expediency and degree of wetlands reclamation will be taken into account. It is quite obvious that such a dense network of drainage channels will no longer exist here. But the protection of the homesteads and buildings of the Demydiv residents will, of course, be ensured. Considerable attention will also be drawn to the need to optimize the design and reduce the cost of the water pumping station operation from the Irpin' River to the Kyiv Reservoir.

Unfortunately, the war did not stop there, but covered the entire east and south of Ukraine. And in such circumstances, numerous reservoirs played an important role both in the defense of the country and in the offensive against the enemy [23]. We will give typical examples of such an ambiguous role of these reservoirs. In particular, on September 14, 2022, Russian troops struck the dam of the Karachuniv reservoir near the city of Kryvyi Rih with missiles in order to sharply raise the water level in the Ingulets River and destroy the pontoon crossings that were used by Ukrainian troops to advance towards the occupied city of Kherson [24]. The rockets hit the sluices of the reservoir dam, which contained more than 300 million cubic meters of water. The flow of water in the Ingulets River rose rapidly by 2 meters, flooded the territories adjacent to the river, including part of the city of Kryvyi Rih, causing considerable damage to the ecological condition of this territory. The civilian population was also affected, whose buildings were heavily flooded. In the Ingulets River, the quality of water has deteriorated, the content of nitrogen and other elements has increased in it. However, this sabotage did not harm the further offensive of Ukrainian troops.

It is also known about the destruction of the Oskol reservoir in the eastern part of Ukraine due to the explosion of one of the gates of the dam as a result of military operations. As a result of the leakage of a significant amount of water, the muddy bottom has been exposed to water and is subject to wind erosion. The hydrological regime of the coastal area has changed. Rare species of flora have been lost. All organisms living in a thick muddy layer will die. The young fish population has been lost as a result of its being washed downstream [25].

Another, but very large-scale and important, could be the consequence of the dam or locks of the Kakhovska HPP destruction during the war. Both the aggressor and the Ukrainian side accuse the opposite side of planning such a dangerous, essentially terrorist act. In a situation where

there is an active offensive of Ukrainian troops to liberate the occupied territory, the destruction of the hydroelectric power station and the flooding of a large area can significantly affect the course of military operations. As the President of Ukraine, Volodymyr Zelenskyy, said in his address to the European Council on October 20, 2022, the Russians are planning to carry out another terrorist attack under a false flag and blame it on Ukraine: “Russia is deliberately creating the basis for a large-scale disaster in the south of Ukraine. We have information that Russian terrorists mined the dam and units of the Kakhovka hydroelectric plant. This is one of the large power facilities. The dam of this hydropower plant holds about 18 million cubic meters of water. If Russian terrorists blow up this dam, more than 80 settlements, including the Kherson, will be in the zone of rapid flooding. Hundreds of thousands of people could be affected. The water supply of a large part of southern Ukraine may be destroyed. This Russian terrorist attack could leave the Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant without water for cooling – water for the ZNPP is taken from the Kakhovka Reservoir. Even the operation of the canal, which was built to supply water to the Crimea and which is periodically allegedly “baked” in Moscow, will be completely destroyed.” [26].

In confirmation of this suspicion, the Main Intelligence Directorate reported that the occupiers mined the Kakhovska HPP back in April, and are now continuing to mine its locks and supports, preparing for such criminal actions. After all, the huge Kakhovka reservoir contains about 18 cubic kilometers of water (or 18 billion cubic meters), accumulated for irrigation, electricity generation, water supply, etc., and the water pressure near the hydroelectric power station is about 16 meters. The breach of the dam will cause a wave of water to fall on the Dnipro (Dnieper) valley and flood the gentle left bank with a large number of settlements and partially the city of Kherson, which is located on the mostly high right bank. But the ecological, economic and security situation will not be limited to destructive processes in the flood zone. As the President rightly pointed out, after such an emergency release of water from the reservoir, the giant Zaporizhzhia nuclear power plant, which uses the water of the Kakhovka Reservoir for cooling units, will be in danger. And hundreds of thousands of hectares of irrigated land in the Kherson Region and the Crimea itself will be in a catastrophic state.

The extent of possible flooding due to the destruction of the hydroelectric station is shown in the Fig. 7, given on the website Glavred newspaper [27]. According to the expert forecasts, the height of the wave after the breach of the dam will be 4.8 m, the speed of the wave – 24.4 km/h, the width of the spill – 5 km, and the duration of flooding will be about 3 days. The rise of water in some places of the zone of catastrophic flooding will reach 8–12 m [28].

Fig. 7. Scheme of the territory flooding after the Kakhovska HPP dam destruction [27]

It should, of course, be noted that the aggressor is also accusing the Ukrainian side of planning to destroy the dam or the locks of the Kakhovska HPP. The Institute for the Study of War reports that Russian sources continue to accuse Ukrainian forces of shelling the Kakhovska HPP and widely distribute graphics showing the path of flooding in the event of a dam breach [29].

In the temporarily occupied territory, messages are sent calling for the evacuation of the population of Nova Kakhovka, allegedly in connection with the preparation of shelling from the side by a subdivision of the Armed Forces. And to reduce possible flooding and destructive processes, significant volumes of water are discharged from the reservoir and its level decreases. The Ukrainian side, for its part, draws the attention of the entire international community to these events in order to prevent such a catastrophe.

4. Conclusions

It is quite obvious that the destruction of reservoirs and damage to the environment will continue until the war ends. And it is necessary to do everything possible so that it ends as soon as possible.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

Financing

The study was performed without financial support.

Data availability

Manuscript has no associated data.

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Received date 12.09.2022

Accepted date 09.11.2022

Published date 30.11.2022

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How to cite: Ladyka, M., Starodubtsev, V. (2022). *Water reservoirs and the war in Ukraine: environmental problems*. *EUREKA: Life Sciences*, 6, 36–43. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21303/2504-5695.2022.002664>